

Plasma polymerized ultra-smooth polypyrrole thin film optical waveguide for integrated optics

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Abstract: An optical waveguide is the key solution in signal propagation as it avoids electromagnetic interference, provides high bandwidth and playing a key role in miniaturization as an immense part of integrated optics. In the current research work, ultra-smooth polypyrrole thin film has been deposited by non-thermal plasma polymerization method by varying input power. Polypyrrole thin film is characterized for structural, optical and mechanical properties. Surface morphology reveals its nanostructured grains which are arranged on a surface in a compact manner. The functional groups are confirmed by FT-IR analysis. π - π^* transitions of electrons is confirmed from optical absorption peak at 340 nm. Optical waveguiding property of polypyrrole thin film is obtained by prism coupling method and found that, optical transmission loss is decreased with power applied and showed 6.28 dB/cm as minimum loss for the film deposited at applied power 12 watt. Adhesion of the polypyrrole thin film is increased, whereas absorption, refractive index, optical band gap, optical transmission loss and roughness of the film are found to decreases with power applied.

Keywords: Polypyrrole, Plasma polymerization, Optical waveguide

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